

Thin Layer Chromatographic Behaviour and Separation of some Carboxylic Acids on Heulandite as a New Adsorbent

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Manuscript received 24 April 1991, revised 5 December 1991, accepted 22 January 1992

Heulandite, a naturally occurring zeolite of 7th group with general formula $\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}_4\text{SiO}_2\text{O}_{82}\cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$, is a crystalline hydrated aluminium silicate of alkali metal with a three-dimensional anion net-work. The mineral occurs principally in cavities in basaltic and related rocks associated with chabazite, stilbite and other zeolites. It may also occur in other volcanic rocks in granite and pegmatites and rarely in gneiss or crystalline schists. Fermor¹ reported heulandite from Bhusawal (India) which shows molecular strain, Roy² described the same mineral from Lonavala Dehu road basalts. In the present work heulandite is used as an adsorbent to study the thin layer chromatographic behaviour of carboxylic acids.

Results and Discussion

R_f values of carboxylic acids were measured under optimum condition (Table 1). For comparison the separation of these carboxylic acids was also studied on silica gel G and H (B.D.H.). Separation of all these nine carboxylic acids in binary, ternary and quaternary mixtures was achieved in single pass 3–4 cm ascending development of solvent in about 3–4 min. Migrations of salicylic, tartaric, maleic and succinic acids from other nonmigratory

acids in their binary mixtures and in some ternary mixtures were achieved on heulandite layers. These acids were also successfully separated on silica gel H except in one case, i.e. separation of tartaric acid from oxalic acid. However clear separations of these acids were not achieved on silica gel G under the comparable experimental conditions.

Thus heulandite has some advantages over silica gel G and silica gel H under the present experimental conditions.

Experimental

The heulandite samples was obtained from Mohanpura, Ujjain in Madhya Pradesh, India. The batch sample was characterised by physico-chemical methods. Ir peaks 3 600–3 400, 1 640, 1 030–980, 880, 780, 720, 602 and 450 cm^{-1} are the same as reported in literature³. In X-ray analysis peaks are reported at glancing angles 10, 17, 19, 21, 22.5, 26.5, 28, 30, 32.5 and 50.5, which tally with the literature values. In T.G. and D.T. analyses, the values are same as reported⁴. In T.G.A., the sample (13.36 g) was heated at the rate of 10°/min. Sample loses no weight upto 50°, loses 8% in the range 81–205° and 2.5% at 248–325°. In D.T.A. peaks are observed at 100, 164, 220, 320 and 430°.

NOTES

TABLE 1— R_f VALUES OF CARBOXYLIC ACIDS ON DIFFERENT ADSORBENTS*

R_f value	Citric acid	Salicylic acid	Tartaric acid	Fumaric acid	Maleic acid	Oxalic acid	Succinic acid	Adipic acid	Hippuric acid
On heulandite	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.51	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.92	0.45
On silica gel H	0.47	0.80	0.58	0.39	1.00	0.61	1.00	0.71	0.46
On silica gel G	0.34	0.00t	0.00t	0.00t	0.44	0.71	0.44	0.45	0.00t

*t=Short tailing.

Heulandite powder as an adsorbent (by passing through 45 μ sieve) without mixing any binder, was made into a slurry in water (concentration 10% w/v) coated on to glass slides (3" x 1") and was activated at 110° for 1 h after air-drying. Migratory behaviour of these carboxylic acids on heulandite was studied in many solvents system of elutropic series. After studying optimum conditions for best separation, benzene-methanol (2.5 : 1, v/v) was selected as the solvent system. Developed spots on tlc plates were detected by spraying with bromo-

cresol purple which gave yellow coloured spots on blue background.

References

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